

ORGANIZING GROUP TRAININGS ON PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT AND SELF-ASSESSMENT

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Abstract. *This study provides information on the mechanisms of organizing individual development and self-assessment through psychological training in the development of training groups. Useful information is provided based on the use of psychological methods by trainers in organizing psychological training. When organizing psychological training, trainers are required to have skills in using psychological methods in training groups. Also, based on the results obtained during our study, information is provided on the pedagogical and psychological rules for organizing training.*

Keywords: *Psychological research, psychologist-trainer, psychological training, psychological interviews, psychological training cases.*

YAKKA RIVOJLANISH VA O'ZINI-O'ZI BAHOLASH BO'YICHA GURUH TRENINGLARNI TASHKILLASHTIRISH

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda trening guruhlarini rivojlantirishda shaxsning yakka rivojlanish va psixologik treninglar orqali o'zini-o'zi baholashni tashkillashtirishning mexanizmlari haqida ma'lumotlar berib o'tiladi. Psixologik treninglarni tashkil qilishda trenerlarning psixologik metodlardan foydalanishlari asosida nazarda tutilgan foydali ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tiladi. Psixologik treninglarni tashkil qilishda trenerlardan trening guruhlariga psixologik metodlardan foydalanish bo'yicha ko'nikmalar talab qilinadi.*

Shuningdek, tadqiqotimiz davomida olingan natijalarga asoslangan holda treninglarni tashkil etishning pedagogik va psixologik qoidalari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Psixologik tadqiqotlar, psixolog-trener, psixologik treninglar, psixologik suhbatlar, psixologik trening holatlari.*

Introduction

Each psychologist-trainer carries out the activity of organizing psychological training in various groups or in various communities. Because, nowadays, there is no person who is excluded from society or does not join a group of people at all, as long as a person lives in society, he is constantly in communication, interacting with various similar individuals. The communication processes of psychologist-trainers always take place in a group of people. In a psychological sense, a group is an association of people united on the basis of common characteristics, common

areas of activity, psychological communication and a common goal. A group is formed by individuals with different levels of thinking, but the psychology of each group differs from the psychology of the individual individuals who make up it and is subject to its own rules.

Knowledge of these laws requires trainers to have extensive experience in managing various types of groups and to know the main criteria for improving the skills of the organizers of these groups. According to information provided in the field of social psychology, psychological training groups are considered small groups. However, for training sessions, this rule changes, that is, training groups of 20-30 people are considered large groups during the training process.

Conducting training and psychological interviews with such large groups can be difficult even for a trainer who is a master of his craft. Given this, it is advisable for a psychologist-trainer to know what to pay attention to when working with a large group. To solve such problems in the training process, it is advisable to divide the group into small groups more often. The goal is to ensure the active participation of each participant in the group in the training. When a topic is discussed in a training group, it is considered a clear situation that it is impossible to ensure the participation of the entire group. This can lead to the complete exclusion of weak participants in the group. If the group is divided into small groups, their active participation is required, and this increases the interest of each participant. The topics discussed in the training usually depend on the position of the trainer or what position he occupies. The peculiarity of training sessions is that the trainer usually appears as part of the group, he does not show his superiority, but occupies an equal position with all participants in the training. One of the main tasks of the trainer is to be a "member of the training group" for the group, for which he should try to be like them in some way. The trainer should remind the participants that everyone has the right to their own opinion or point of view, and this opinion or point of view should be respected by those around them. It is not necessary to agree with them completely, that is, to support them even if their opinion is wrong, but to argue and discuss with them, but to maintain openness, sincerity and respect. This type of relationship creates an atmosphere of mutual respect and trust and helps to organize a constructive discussion of the problem. If the trainer participates in all exercises and discussions during the training, shares his thoughts and opinions, does not hide his mistakes in some cases, makes mistakes in the exercises, this will help him to treat the participants as equals. The stage of the psychologist-trainer's work is the main part of the participants' achievement of their goals.

Participants follow the rules of working in a group.

Trust in each other arises due to the opportunity to ask for mutual help. As a result, if they do not agree with some of the trainer's opinions, they may become dissatisfied with the trainer, and in some cases become nervous, depressed. The trainer's task is to help build trusting relationships in the group, not to ignore the events in the group, monitor the group dynamics, conduct games that eliminate dissatisfaction and nervousness in the group, and help build trusting relationships in the group. The training completion stage is the logical point of the end of the training; if the training was successful, the mood of all participants will be excellent. At this stage, there is an opportunity to smooth out some of the shortcomings made during the work.

The stage should be well thought out and clearly organized; it cannot be carried out randomly. Because such psychological relationships can enhance a positive or negative assessment of the training.

The trainer's task is to prepare and conduct the final event in a positive spirit, create comfortable conditions for each participant, create an opportunity to thank each other or the trainer, and express gratitude to each participant in their own way. According to group psychology, when strangers gather in one place, a certain tension arises in the group. If this law is applied to training groups, then situations of obvious tension arise in a place where people who are completely strangers to each other gather. The trainer's task from the very beginning of the training is to try to alleviate this tension as much as possible. To do this, the trainer must carefully think over a plan for working with the group so that uncomfortable situations do not arise in the group or that the uncomfortable situations that have arisen are eliminated. The trainer should also know the specifics of the stages and mechanisms of group dynamics, that is, the group has several stages of development. If we answer the questions about what trainers should do in such cases: to get out of such situations, the trainer should refer to the rules of behavior and actions that must be followed during all practical and theoretical training sessions developed together with the participants. To enhance the effect of the rules, it is recommended to organize role-playing games with the participants at the beginning of days 3 and 5, it will be more effective if each group shows solidarity. If a conflict arises between participants or subgroups in the group, it should be resolved constructively. What the trainer should do in this case: he should try to talk to the participant individually; if there is only one such participant in the group, he should create an opportunity for him to express his inner feelings; We should talk about what bothers him, what makes him angry, and what is the basis of his hatred for people. Psychologist-trainers should try to reduce or eliminate negative emotions in them by using active work methods, that is, games that reduce fatigue and aggression.

Experiences observed in many psychological training sessions show that conflicts can arise in the process of work between group members, between small groups, or in the relationship between the leader and the participant. When conducting a training session, the trainer should be aware that each group has an individual aspect. Accordingly, the implementation of the program and plan within a given problem in different groups will be different. If the trainer's work goes smoothly in one group, then in another he may encounter certain problems. With this in mind, let's look at the most common problems that occur during training: We can observe the emergence of small groups within the group. In the initial stage, on the first day of group activity, most participants experience feelings of anxiety as a result of not knowing each other and the trainer.

According to information provided in social psychology, training groups are small groups.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that it is important for a psychologist-trainer to be experienced in the formation of individual development and self-assessment indicators of a person through psychological training. We believe that the use of training sessions based on the results of psychological research can give good results in improving the basic skills of a person's self-assessment during the training process. The results of psychological research have shown that psychological trainings are useful psychological methods for increasing human development indicators and preventing conflict situations.

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